

Prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* in some street vended ready-to-eat meat products in Birnin Kebbi metropolis: A potential food safety threat

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to determine the prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Street vended *Balangu*, *Kilishi* and *Tsire* meat products in Birnin kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria. Sixty six (66) samples (*tsire*-21, *Kilishi*-21 and *Balangu*-24), were purchased from street vendors and transferred for microbiological analyses. Microbiological analyses were conducted according to standard culture procedure involving isolation in general and selective media for isolation and identification of isolates, followed by series of biochemical tests for confirmation of isolates. Data was analyzed and expressed as colony forming units per gram of sample (cfu/g). Results revealed bacterial load and presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from the RTE-MPs. The total bacterial counts for *tsire*, *balangu* and *kilishi* were found to be 1.34, 1.71 and 2.01×10⁶ cfu/g, respectively. Also, the *Staphylococcus aureus* population isolated from *tsire*, *balangu* and *kilishi* were recorded as 0.14, 0.29 and 0.33×10⁴ cfu/g, respectively. In terms of public health significance, the results of the current study placed the studied RTE-MPs consumed in the study area within unsatisfactory limits since the values are more than log 9×10⁶ recommended to be acceptable in related RTE-MPs. However, the value for *Staphylococcus aureus* was satisfactory since it was found to be within the limits of <20×10⁴cfu/g recommended by the satisfactory limits for consumption. It was concluded that the high bacterial count observed and the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* in the RTE-MPs are of public health significance since they could pose health risks. Good manufacturing practices in the production and consumption of RTE-MPs were recommended to improve their safety and quality.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Food safety is a significant and growing public health problem in Nigeria and the world at large, since food-borne diseases are important contributors to the huge burden of sickness and death of humans. The Nigerian Federal Ministry of Health reported 90,000 cases of food poisoning in 2007 [1]. However, that was a gross underestimate since most cases of gastroenteritis are not reported to hospitals or concerned bodies, rather, patients resort to the use of over-the-counter antidiarrheal drugs as previously reported [2-3]. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated 200,000 deaths

from diarrhea each year in Nigeria (WHO, 2008), as many as 70% of which may be attributable to contaminated food and water.

Presence of pathogens in food products imposes potential hazard for consumers and causes grave losses in both economic and human productivity through food-borne diseases. Symptoms include nausea, vomiting, and abdominal cramps with or without diarrhea. Preventive measures include safe food handling and processing practice, maintaining cold chain, adequate cleaning and disinfection of equipment, prevention of cross-contamination in

home and kitchen, and prevention of contamination from farm to fork [4].

Meat products (RTE-MPs) including intermediate moisture meats like *balangu* (berbacue), *tsire* (skewed meat), *guru* (roasted chicken) and dried meat products like *kilishi* (jerky), *dambun nama* (meat floss), *banda* (dried meat), were reported to be highly appreciated because of their characteristic taste, texture and storage stability [5].

However, according to Aworh [6], a major source of concern, from a public health standpoint as revealed by consumer surveys, is the unhygienic conditions under which meat products are often processed and retailed in Nigeria and other West African countries. FSAI [7] reported that during processing, handling, packaging and storage, these products are liable to contamination by pathogenic biological agents that could result in food poisoning.

Staphylococcus aureus (*S. aureus*) is a bacterium that causes staphylococcal food poisoning, a form of gastroenteritis with rapid onset of symptoms. *S. aureus* is commonly found in the environment (soil, water and air) and is also found in the nose and on the skin of humans. Staphylococcal food-borne disease (SFD) is one of the most common food-borne diseases worldwide resulting from the contamination of food by preformed *S. aureus* enterotoxins [8].

Elsewhere, several studies have documented prevalence of *S. aureus* in many food products including meat and its products, indicating that consumers are at potential risk of *S. aureus* colonization and subsequent infection [9]. There are little or no documented records of such studies in Kebbi state. Hence, the aim of this work is to determine the Prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* in some Street Vended *Balangu*, *Kilishi* and *Tsire* meat products in Birnin kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted in Kebbi State, North-West region of Nigeria. The study area is located between Latitudes 11°30' and 12°16'N, and Longitudes 4°00' and 6°25'E. Kebbi State lies in the Savanna regions of Nigeria with its characteristic grasslands and isolated hills. The study Area has an annual average temperature of 28.3°C and the maximum daytime temperature could reach a little above 40°C [10].

The area is known for its abundance of livestock especially the popular Sokoto *Gudali*, *Uda* and *Yankasa* sheep, Sokoto red goat, and many poultry species like domestic fowls, guinea fowls and turkeys, and many other breeds of livestock [11]. According to [18], among all the livestock that makes up the farm animals in Nigeria, ruminants, comprising sheep, goats and cattle, constitute the farm animals largely reared by farm families in the country's agricultural system

The State has a variety of animal products that are obtained from the vast kinds of animals available in the region of which meat products predominates [12,13]. This could be evident from the many RTE meat joints sighted along major roads in both urban and rural areas of the region [14].

2.1.1 Sampling of ready-to-eat meat products and sample size

A total of sixty six (66) samples of RTE-MPs, comprising of *balangu*(24), *Kilishi*(21) and *Tsire*(21) were purchased from 14 different locations in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis.all the samples were obtained from both on the spot processors and street vendors. The samples were carefully collected and packed in polyethene bags and stored in ice packed coolers, then transferred to the laboratory for microbiological analyses.

Table 1. Layout for sample collection.

Sampling location	Samples by Rte-mp type			Total
	Bal	Kili	Tsire	
A	1	1	1	3
B	4	3	4	11
C	2	3	3	8
D	2	1	2	5
E	3	3	3	9
F	1	1	1	3
G	6	6	6	18
H	2	2	1	5
I	3	1	0	4
Total	24	21	21	66

2.2 Microbiological Procedures

Microbiological analyses were conducted according to the procedures described by [15]. The microbiological analyses involved isolation in general (non-selective) and selective media for isolation and identification of isolates, followed by series of biochemical tests for confirmation of isolates.

2.2.1 Non-selective pre-enrichment using general medium for Total Bacterial Count

Twenty five grams of each RTE-MP sample was picked, minced and homogenized. Then one gram (1g) of the homogenized sample was weighed out and homogenized in 9mls buffered peptone water (LabM, UK) and hand shaken for two minutes to give a dilution of 1:10. A six-fold serial dilution was then prepared by pipetting 1 ml of the homogenate into the first test tube containing 9 ml of buffered peptone water to make the first dilution. From the first dilution, 1ml was taken and pipetted into the second test tube containing 9ml of diluent. The process was repeated until the sixth dilution was made and 1ml from the last dilution was removed and discarded.

The pour plating method was used for colony counting. Petridishes were prepared and labelled according to samples and dilutions selected. For aerobic plate count determination, about 10-12 ml of the molten Nutrient agar (Biomark, India) (cooled to 42-45°C) was poured into each petridish within 15 minutes from the time of preparation of the original dilution. 1 ml each from dilutions 10^2 , 10^4 and 10^6 for every sample was respectively poured on a prelabelled petri plates. The media and dilutions were mixed gently swirling clockwise and anticlockwise, to and fro taking care that the mixture did not touch the lid and was allowed to set. The plates were incubated inverted for 48 hrs at 35°C. Distinct colonies on on plates were counted using a digital colony counting chamber (Quebec colony counter, Reichert, USA) and recorded per dilution counted. The actual number of colonies on dishes containing 30-300 colonies was counted and recorded.

2.2.2 Selective enrichment using specific media for pathogen isolation

2.2.2.1 Identification and confirmation of *Staphylococcus aureus*

The pre-enrichment was carried out by 25g of the RTE-MP into a sterile jar and 225ml of

buffered peptone water was added. The jar was capped and shaken thoroughly for two minutes. 1ml of the homogenate was pipetted in 9ml of peptone water and mixed well using a votex mixer. 1ml of the homogenate was transferred into triplicate plates of Mannitol salt agar (MSA). The plates were incubated in an upright position in the 35-37°C incubator for about 1hrs or until inoculum is absorbed by the medium, then the plates were inverted and incubated for 45-48 hrs. Catalase and coagulase tests were used to confirm *S. aureus*.

2.3 Biochemical Tests

Identification of isolates was conducted based on established conventional cultural, morphological and biochemical characterizations. The biochemical tests conducted were Gram staining, Mannitol salt agar, catalase and coagulate tests using methods as previously described [16].

2.4 Data analysis

2.4.1 Determination of total bacterial count and prevalence of pathogens in RTE-MPs

The colony forming unit per gram of the samples was calculated and results expressed as colony forming unit per gram of meat sample (cfu/g) using the following expression by FSSAI [15]:

$$CFU = \frac{\Sigma C}{(N1 + 0.1N2)D}$$

Where:

CFU = colony forming units;

ΣC = sum of all the colonies counted on all dishes retained;

N1 = number of dishes retained in first dilution;

N2 = number of dishes retained in the second dilution;

0.1 = constant;

D = dilution factor corresponding to the first dilution.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the bacterial load and presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from some RTE-MPs. Out of the 66 samples collected, only 17 were found to be contaminated with *Staphylococcus aureus*. The total bacterial counts for *tsire*, *balangu* and *kilishi* were found to be 1.34, 1.71 and 2.01×10^6 cfu/g, respectively. Also, the *Staphylococcus aureus* population isolated from *tsire*, *balangu* and *kilishi* were recorded as 0.14, 0.29 and 0.33×10^4 cfu/g, respectively.

Table 2. Bacterial load and presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from some RTE-MPs in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State.

Rte-mp	No. of samples	Mean TBC	<i>S. aureus</i> pop.
Balangu	24	16.85×10^6 cfu/g	0.29×10^4 cfu/g
Kilishi	21	19.82×10^6 cfu/g	0.33×10^4 cfu/g
Tsire	21	13.36×10^6 cfu/g	0.14×10^4 cfu/g
Total	66		

The variation in colony counts could be as a result of variations in processing and handling methods where *tsire*, and *balangu* at post-lethality, are in most cases kept warm around embers which could assist in killing the bacterial population unlike *kilishi* which are usually displayed in open trays and table tops, making the product more vulnerable to bacterial contamination. The lower counts in *tsire* could also be due to the presence of spices added during processing which were reported to have a significant anti-microbial and anti-oxidant effects [17,18]. In most cases, *balangu* is processed without addition of spices but could be added while serving. Previous research works reported comparatively similar results for the products. [19] recorded similar total plate counts in suya samples in the order of $\times 10^5$ and $\times 10^6$ cfu/g. [13] isolated a range of 0.07 – 2.22×10^5 cfu/g from *suya* collected from different locations.

In terms of public health significance, the results

of the current study placed the studied RTE-MPs consumed in the study area within unsatisfactory limits according to [20,23] standards since the values are more than $\log 9 \times 10^6$ recommended to be acceptable in related RTE-MPs. However, the value for *Staphylococcus aureus* was satisfactory since it was found to be within the limits of $< 20 \times 10^4$ cfu/g recommended by [21] to be the satisfactory limits. In Nigeria, similar results were reported for various RTE-MPs such as [13] who recorded *S. aureus* range of 0.53 – 1.67×10^5 in *balangu*. [22] reported 3.1×10^2 of *S. aureus* isolated from chicken RTE-MP. Higher isolates were recorded by [23] from *suya* with *S. aureus* ranging between $\log 0.0$ and 6.25×10^5 cfu/g. The current study revealed that *Kilishi* had higher TBC, and individual bacterial counts than *kilishi* and *tsire*. Incidentally, *balangu* was the commonly consumed among the identified product in the study area. Figure 1 shows the prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* among *tsire*, *balangu* and *kilishi*.

Figure 1. Prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* among *tsire*, *balangu* and *kilishi*.

4. CONCLUSION

Staphylococcus aureus was found to be prevalent in the three RTE-MPs studied in the study area, hence, consumers are exposed to risks of infections. It was concluded that the high bacterial count observed and the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* in the RTE-MPs are of public health significance since they could pose health risks. Good manufacturing practices in the production and consumption of RTE-MPs were recommended to improve their safety and quality.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

MIR designed the study, conducted the laboratory experiments, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. SSM assisted in the the

literature searches and organization of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript."

REFERENCES

1. WHO (2008). Food-borne disease outbreaks, Guidelines for investigation and control. WHO Press, Geneva, Switzerland. Retrieved online on 14th November, 2015, from: www.who.int/foodsafety/publications/foodborne_disease/outbreak_guidelines.pdf
2. Menendez D, Bendesky A, Rojas E, Salamanca F and Ostrosky-Wegman P (2002). Role of P53 functionality in the genotoxicity of metronidazole and its hydroxy metabolite. *Mutat Res*, 25; 501(1-2): 57-67.
3. Sarfaraz S, Shakeel F, Sajjad F, Haider K, Urooba F, Siddique AS (2015). Abuse of Prescription Drug Metronidazole in Diarrhea by Laymen Population of Karachi. *Eur J Pharm Med Res*, 2(7), 28-32.

4. Jhalka K, Tara CS and Dipendra T (2014). *Staphylococcus aureus* and Staphylococcal Food-Borne Disease. An Ongoing Challenge in Public Health: Review. *BioMed Res Interl*, 3(4):432-438.
5. Ribah MI, Jibir M, Muhammad N and Shinkafi BA (2013). Effect of Tenderizers on Organoleptic Properties of *Banda*- A Nigerian Dehydrated Meat. *Proc. 18th Ann. Conf. of the Ani. Sci. Ass. of Nigeria*, Abuja, 8th-12th Sept, 2013.
6. Aworh CO (2008). The role of traditional food processing technologies in national development: the West African experience, in G. Robertson (Ed.), *Using Science And Technology To Improve Nutrition And Promote National Development. Intl Union Food Sci Tech*, 2008:54-61.
7. FSAI (2005). *The Control and Management of Listeria monocytogenes Contamination of Food*. Published by Food Safety Authority of Ireland, p.104.
8. Figueroa G, Navarrete P, Caro M, Troncoso M and Faundez G (2002). Carriage of enterotoxigenic *Staphylococcus aureus* in food handlers. *Revista Medica De Chile*, 130(8):859-864.
9. Aydin A, Sudagidan M and Muratoglu K (2011). Prevalence of staphylococcal enterotoxins, toxin genes and genetic relatedness of foodborne *Staphylococcus aureus* strains isolated in the Marmara region of Turkey. *Intl. J. Food Micr*, 148:99-106.
10. Collins B (2005). *Nigeria Maps*. Published by Spectrum books Limited, Ibadan, Nigeria.
11. Roger B (1999). *Traditional Livestock Breeds: Geographical Distribution and Dynamics in Relation to the Ecology of West Africa*. Overseas Development Institute, Portland House, Stag Place. *Working Paper 122*. October, 1999.
12. Lawal-Adebawale OA (2012). *Livestock Production. Dynamics of Ruminant Livestock Management in the Context of the Nigerian Agricultural System* (Chapter 4). Khalid, J. (Ed.). Published under CCBY, pp. 324.
13. Edema MO, Osho AT and Diala CI (2008). Evaluation of microbial hazards associated with the processing of *Suya* (a grilled meat product). *Sci Res Essay*, 3(12):621-626.
14. Muhammad BF and Umar AM (2010). Processing Beef into Tsire and Balangu: Effects on Proximate Composition and Amino Acid Profile. *Sav J Agric*, 5:61-69.
15. FSSAI. *Manual of methods of analysis of foods*. Food safety and standards of india. Lab manual-14. Ministry of health and family welfare, new delhi, india. P 105;2012.
16. Ruangpan L. and Tendencia EA (2010). Bacterial Isolation, Identification and Storage. In *Laboratory manual of standardized methods for antimicrobial sensitivity tests for bacteria isolated from aquatic animals and environment* (pp. 3-11).
17. Umoru FP, Agbaye AW, Lamidi AS, Ajibade ASA, Labaeka AA, Falade RA, *et al* (2013). Body weight and carcass characteristics of broiler chicken fed mixture of ginger (*zingiber officinale*) and garlic (*Allium sativum*) in diets. *Proceedings of the 47th Annual Conference of the Agricultural Society of Nigeria*, Ibadan, 2013;1101-1105.
18. Ndelekwute EK, Uzegbu HO, Assam ED and Udorok UE (2015). Influence of black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) as growth promoter on performance of starter broiler chicks. *Proc. 40th Ann. Conf. Nigerian Society for Animal Production, 15-19th March 2015*, NAPRI/ABU, Zaria, pp. 330-333.
19. Inyang CU, Igyor, MA. and Uma EN (2005). Bacteria Quality of a Smoked Meat Product "Suya", *Nig Food J*, 23:239-240.
20. ICMSF (1996). *Microorganisms in foods 2. Sampling for microbiological analysis: Principles and specific applications*. International Commission on Microbiological Specification for foods, University of Toronto press.
21. HPA (2009). *Guidelines for Assessing the Microbiological Safety of Ready-to-Eat Foods*. Health Protection Agency. 7th Floor, Holborn Gate. 330 High Holborn, London, p. 34.
22. Yuksek N, Evrensel SS, Temelli S, Anar S and Sen MKC (2009). A Microbiological Evaluation on the Ready-To-Eat Red Meat and Chicken Donair Kebabs from a Local Catering Company in Bursa. *J Biol & Environ Sci*, 3(7): 7-10.
23. Ogbonna IO, Danladi MS, Akinmusire O and Odu CE (2012). Microbiological Safety and Proximate Composition of *Suya* Stored at Ambient Temperature for Six Hours from Maiduguri, Northern Nigeria. *Internet J Food Saf*, 14:11-16.